

Modeling High Temperature Cross-linking Between Graphitic Surfaces and Glassy Carbon

Jacob R. Gissing
Stevens Institute of Technology
Chemical Engineering and Materials Science

jgissing@stevens.edu
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Molecular Dynamics (MD) for Nanoscale Insight

- Molecular dynamics (MD) is a computer simulation technique for modeling the motion and interaction of atoms and molecules
- Atomic positions are updated using a small timestep and Newtonian mechanics, $a = F/m$
- In traditional MD, bonded connections are defined once at beginning of simulation and not changed during the simulation
- Mechanical properties can be predicted at the nanoscale (ultimate strength, elastic modulus, interfacial shear strength)

Nanocomposites have Advanced Properties

- Composites have replaced many components of aircraft, cars, sports equipment and other technologies such as energy storage
- Interfaces and defects are nucleation sites for mechanical failure
- Failure mechanisms of composite materials are complex, and difficult to relate back to processing conditions
- Molecular dynamics (MD) models can help us understand the origin and propagation of material failure
- **Grand Challenge: Developing Materials that can Serve Both as Temperature-Resistant and High-Strength Structural Components**

Aerospacelike

Automotive

NASA's Orion spacecraft recovered after Artemis I test flight

Interfacial Interactions are Critical

- The properties of composite materials remain well below their theoretical values
- Interfacial interactions and defects often determine the material's ultimate properties!
- Embedded interfaces are difficult to probe using experimental techniques
- Atomistic MD can predict the properties and dynamic response of complex multicomponent systems

Tensile tests of CNT fiber reinforced polymer composites.

Kim et al. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* (2023): 107449.

Why is Char Yield Important?

- Char yield is the amount of material left over after subjecting it to high temperature pyrolysis
 - Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is used to obtain plots of mass vs time and/or temperature (typically ramped up to 800°C -1000°C)
- High char materials require fewer cycles of carbonization and resin infiltration to achieve desired properties

Prior Efforts to Predict Char Yield

- Correlate existing literature data with empirical formulas
 - Element ratios, molecular group analysis, quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR)
 - Achieves reasonable correlations with low-char yield resins
- Not enough chemical intuition to predict outlier behavior

Molar group contribution values.

Chemical group ^a	Type ^b	Molar group contributions			Ψ_i/M_i J/g K
		Ω_i MJ/mol	X_i g/mol	Ψ_i kJ/mol K	
-C(CH ₃) ₂ -	B	2.63	0	85.5	2036
-CH ₃	S	0.50	0	18.5	1233
-CH ₂ -	B	0.51	0	14.4	1029
	S	4.84	0	108.6	855
-O-	B	0.12	0	11.1	694

Lyon, Richard E., et al. "A Molecular Basis for Polymer Flammability." *Polymer* 50, no. 12, 2608–17 (2009).

Large-Scale Reactive MD is Challenging

- Quantum mechanics can model reactions from first principles
- Levels of abstraction come with a tradeoff: accuracy vs. speed
- Reactive force fields can achieve near-DFT accuracy
 - Much faster than DFT, much slower than classical molecular dynamics (MD)

Gissinger et al. "Modeling chemical reactions in classical molecular dynamics simulations." *Polymer* 128 (2017): 211-217.

Case Study: Carbonization Reactions

- Starting point: diethynylbenzene polymerized via linear and cyclotrimerization reactions
- Define carbonization moves from polymerized polyarylacetylene (PAA) motifs, as well as ring-closing and Diels-Alder reaction
- End goal: Approximate model of the carbonization and/or graphitization process

Case Study: Nanoribbon Formation

Slice is 7 Å thick; only rings shown

After ~99% polymerization and ~14.5K carbonization reactions

Expedient large-scale model for early-stage pyrolysis of polyarylacetylene (200K atoms)

Density: 1.0 g/cm³
Box Size: 13.8 nm

ReaxFF: Inherently Reactive Model

- Reactive force field that does not require explicit input of reaction mechanisms
 - Based on bond order formulation (see definition below)
- Trained on DFT data: small molecules for reactions and graphitic structures for mechanical properties
- Effective method for smaller-scale simulations that involve complex chemical transformations

$$E_{\text{system}} = E_{\text{bond}} + E_{\text{over}} + E_{\text{under}} + E_{\text{val}} + E_{\text{pen}} + E_{\text{tors}} + E_{\text{conj}} + E_{\text{vdWaals}} + E_{\text{Coulomb}}$$

van Duin et al. "ReaxFF: A Reactive Force Field for Hydrocarbons." The Journal of Physical Chemistry A 105, no. 41, 9396–9409 (2001).

Char Yield Simulation Protocol

- Temperature ramp cycle
 - 300 K - 3000 K at 10 K/ps
 - High temperatures/rates to accelerate reactions
- Anneal at high pressure (1 GPa) to achieve final densities of 1.8 g/cm³ - 2.0 g/cm³
- ReaxFF with periodic removal of outgassing products to allow for carbonization and densification
- Initial system size: 36000 atoms

Char Yield Results for Various Chemistries

- Simulation protocol able to accurately predict char yield trends across a wide range of functional groups, heteroatom content and char yield values
- Chemically specific method
- No assumptions or fitting of experimental results

Gissinger et al. "Predicting char yield of high-temperature resins." *Carbon* 202 (2023): 336-347.

Mechanical Properties of Glassy Carbon

- Nonporous char morphology results in high predicted elastic moduli
- Predicted values in expected range for glassy carbon (~ 30 GPa @ 1.5 g/cm³), but far lower than high modulus carbon fibers
- Highlights importance of achieving structures with high density and low defects, porosity

Strain to Failure

PAA, 40% strain

Specific Stress (GPa/(g/cm³))

Carbon Hybridization/Heteroatoms Evolution

Ternary 'glassy carbon' phase diagram. Axes = fractional number of atoms

Final Morphology: Ring Distribution

- Final carbonized structure consists primarily of fused five-, six- and seven-membered carbon rings
- Twice as many six-membered rings as other sizes, but rings are well distributed with respect to ring size
- Similar final morphology obtained for lower char yield resins

Cyanate ester (BADCY)

Gissinger et al. *Carbon* 202 (2023): 336-347.

49.8 Å

57.6 Å

Polyarylacetylene (PAA)

■ Five-membered ring ■ Six-membered ring ■ Seven-membered ring

Topological Analysis: Cluster Definition

These two rings form a bridge (i.e., disconnecting them creates two molecules)

Two clusters

One cluster (no bridges, i.e. each fused ring pair shares at least one other ring)

Final Morphology: Cluster Distribution

PAA

BADCY

Final Morphology: Cluster Distribution

PAA, largest cluster

PAA, top four largest clusters

Outgassing Products

- Protocol keeps track of molecules removed from the system to mimic outgassing
- Primarily CO for oxygen-containing resins (highly stable bond)
- Useful metric to compare to experimental techniques such as TGA-mass spectrometry to confirm the chemistry is being captured accurately

TGA: Thermal Gravimetric Analysis

Tools for Direct Experimental Comparison

- Simulated XRD pattern allows for direct comparison with experimental morphologies
- Curve is typical of non-graphitized glassy carbon at lower carbonization temperatures
- The 002 peak, which indicates graphitic structure, notably sharpens after increasing the annealing time

Simulating High-Resolution Microscopy

Experimental HRTEM vs. carbonization temperature

Jurkiewicz, Karolina, et al. "Evolution of glassy carbon under heat treatment: correlation structure–mechanical properties." *Journal of materials science* 53.5 (2018): 3509-3523.

Simulated microscopy consistent with non-graphitized glassy carbon at lower temperatures

Adding Interfaces to the Model

- Triple-layer graphene inserted into initial monomer configuration for composite model
- Bulk PAN char: 54 wt%, 1.76 g/cm³
- Confined PAN: 42 wt%, 1.96 g/cm³
- Significantly larger regions of fused six-membered rings observed at interface due to templating effect of graphene

PAN char (graphene hidden)

Neat vs Confined Resin Char Yields

- Char yields for confined resins in composite systems matched those recorded for neat resin
- Implies that prediction of char yield is mostly independent of degree of confinement for this modeling protocol
- Technical Note: Graphene sheets should remain mobile to obtain realistic results

Reactivity at the Graphene Sheet Interface

- It was critical to keep graphene surface mobile to achieve charring behavior
- At each graphene-resin interface ($\sim 46 \text{ nm}^2$), crosslinking occurred at ~ 7 sites, often involving two or more adjacent crosslinks that distort the surface

Non-resin-facing side of graphene sheets with crosslinks indicated

Above, graphene sheets in gray and resin char in color

Promising Method for Predicting Char Yield

- A chemically specific protocol was developed to predict char yield for high temperature resins
 - No prior knowledge of high-temperature behavior required
- Validated for low, medium and high char yield resins with various chemical structures and number of heteroatoms
- Additional outputs include atomistic structure, composition, morphology, mechanical properties, chemical pathways, outgassing products
- Currently being used to investigate and screen new chemistries

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Langley
Research
Center

AFRL
AIR FORCE RESEARCH LABORATORY

Email (Jake Gissing): jgissing@stevens.edu

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P1 (phthalonitrile): Hu, Y. et al. RSC Advances, 8, 32899, 2018.

BADCY (bisphenol A dicyanate ester): Wang, Y. et al. Polymer, 77, 354, 2015.

PAN (polyacrylonitrile): Song, C. et al. J Porous Materials, 16, 197, 2009.

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